

THE ROLE OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN THE FUTURE OF ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHING

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ANNOTATSIYA

Mazkur maqolada ingliz tilini o'qitishdagi sun'iy intellektning o'рни hamda uning o'qituvchi roliga ta'siri tahlil qilinadi. Tadqiqot davomida miqdoriy metoddan foydalanilib, Google Forms orqali 12 kishi orasida so'rovnomma o'tkazildi. Natijalar shuni ko'rsatdiki, respondentlarning aksariyati sun'iy intellekt vositalaridan muntazam foydalanadi va bu vositalar ayniqsa, speaking hamda writing ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirishda samarali hisoblanadi. Shu bilan birga, respondentlarning ko'pchiligi o'qituvchilar hali ham ta'lim jarayonida muhim rol o'ynashini ta'kidladilar. Tadqiqot natijalariga ko'ra shu aniq bo'ldiki, sun'iy intellekt o'qituvchining ro'lini to'liq egallab olmaydi, balki ta'lim jarayonini yanada boyituvchi, qo'llab-quvvatlovchi vosita sifatida xizmat qiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: sun'iy intellekt, ingliz tili, til o'qitish, AI tools, ChatGPT, o'qituvchi ro'li, ta'lim texnologiyalari.

АННОТАЦИЯ

В данной статье анализируется роль искусственного интеллекта в обучении английскому языку и его влияние на роль преподавателя. В ходе исследования был использован количественный метод, а данные были собраны посредством опроса через Google Forms среди 12 респондентов. Результаты показали, что большинство участников регулярно используют инструменты искусственного интеллекта и считают их особенно полезными для развития навыков speaking и writing. Однако большинство респондентов также отметили важную роль преподавателя в образовательном процессе. Исследование показывает, что искусственный интеллект не может полностью заменить преподавателя, а скорее служит вспомогательным инструментом в обучении.

Ключевые слова: искусственный интеллект, английский язык, обучение языкам, AI tools, ChatGPT, роль преподавателя, образовательные технологии.

ANNOTATION

This article examines the role of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in English language teaching. And also its influence on the role of teachers. A quantitative research method was used, and data were collected through a Google Forms survey involving 12 respondents. The findings showed that most participants regularly use AI tools and consider them effective, especially in improving speaking and writing skills. At the same time, the majority of respondents emphasized that teachers still play an important role in the learning process. The study concludes that AI cannot completely replace teachers. Instead, it should be considered a supportive educational tool.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, English language learning, AI tools, ChatGPT, teacher's role, educational technology.

INTRODUCTION

Technology has changed the way students learn languages, especially in the last few years. Particularly in foreign language education, digital technologies and Artificial Intelligence (AI) have changed traditional methods of teaching and learning. Many students now use mobile apps, online platforms, and AI tools to practice English outside the classroom. According to John McCarthy [2007], Artificial Intelligence refers to intelligent machines capable of performing tasks that normally require human intelligence. In language learning, AI tools are useful because they can give quick feedback and allow students to practice more independently. Also, tools such as ChatGPT, Grammarly, and online translation platforms help students practice writing, speaking, and vocabulary more effectively. Vygotsky [1978] emphasized that interaction and guidance play an essential role in the learning process. Therefore, the growing use of AI has made important questions if the teachers are still important in modern classrooms. Some researchers argue that AI can increase students' motivation and make learning more accessible [Holmes, Bialik, & Fadel, 2019]. But others believe that emotional support that only human can provide and classroom management cannot be fully replaced by technology. In many educational institutions, electronic boards, televisions, and other digital devices are already used in classrooms. However, some teachers still face difficulties in using these technologies effectively. Because of this development, many people have started to question whether AI can replace teachers in the future. Therefore, this study aims to explore how AI tools influence the role of teachers in English language learning.

Research Question

How does the use of AI tools influence the role of teachers in English language learning?

METHODS

In this research, a quantitative research method was used. In order to gather information, a survey was conducted through Google Forms. Twelve respondents who study English participated in the survey. The participants belonged to different age groups and English proficiency levels. The questionnaire consisted of 12 questions related to the use of AI tools in language learning, their effectiveness, and students' opinions about the role of teachers in education that AI is used. The responses were analyzed in percentages to understand students' opinions about AI in English learning. The questionnaire asked students how often they use AI tools and which language skills they improve with them.

RESULTS

Most of the participants were between 18 and 22 years old. This indicates that the research mainly reflects the opinions of young English learners. Additionally, most participants (76.9%) reported using AI tools on a daily basis, while only a small percentage stated that they use such technologies rarely. Furthermore, 84.6% of respondents agreed that AI tools help improve their English language skills. The findings also showed that participants considered AI is useful for improving speaking skills (38.5%) and writing skills (30.8%). This shows that many students already use AI tools in their daily English practice. However, when asked about the future role of teachers, 46.2% of respondents were uncertain whether AI could replace teachers, while 38.5% believed that teachers would still remain important in the educational process. Only a small share thought that AI could completely replace teachers. Many participants also mentioned that AI tools make learning more interesting and motivating.

DISCUSSION

The study shows that students prefer AI tools because they are easy to access and help them get quick feedback. Students use AI technologies not only for grammar correction and vocabulary learning but participants mostly used AI for speaking practice. Many of them also said it helped their writing. Some participants mentioned that AI tools are helpful because they are available at any time. These results support the ideas of Holmes, Bialik, and Fadel [2019], who stated that Artificial Intelligence can make education more flexible, interactive, and student-centered. Even though AI is becoming more common, students still believe teachers are important. This may be explained by the fact that teachers provide emotional support, motivation, classroom interaction, and guidance, which AI systems cannot fully offer. According to Vygotsky [1978], social interaction is one of the key factors in effective learning. Therefore, although AI can support independent learning, the role of teachers remains important in the educational process. The study also shows that students are still uncertain about the possibility of AI completely replacing teachers in the future. This may be because technology is developing quickly, but human interaction is still necessary in education.

Overall, AI should be seen as a tool that supports teachers rather than replace them.

CONCLUSION

Today, AI plays an important role in English language learning. AI tools help students improve different language skills and increase motivation. In particular, students find AI effective in improving speaking and writing skills. However, despite the advantages of AI technologies, teachers still play a crucial role in education. Most participants believed that teachers will still be necessary even if AI continues to develop. Instead, AI and teachers should work together to create a more effective and interactive learning environment. Future research with more participants could give clearer results about the effects of AI in language learning and teachers' role.

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